

Radio advertising influence, selection factors and advertisers' satisfaction of radio broadcasting in one city

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ABSTRACT

Radio for advertisers is often seen as an outdated type of media. Today, the media is changing rapidly to digitalization and on-line advertising, which can be seen in radio as well. This study aims to determine the influence of radio advertisement, client radio-selection factors, and client satisfaction of radio broadcasting. Using a validated survey questionnaire and desk and filed research conducted by the researchers themselves, a descriptive research design was used to examine the 27 local advertisers of a single radio station in one city of the Province of Negros Occidental, Philippines. The advertisers were grouped according to their nature of business, organization type, length of advertising engagement, client type, and advertising package. The Mean, the Mann Whitney-U, and the Kruskal-Wallis were utilized for viewing and analyzing the study's outcomes. Findings revealed that the influence of radio advertisement is generally high. Specifically, results showed that the influence of radio advertisement on sales is high while moderate on market shares and the extent of radio selection factors is high. The study also revealed that advertisement cost is of utmost consideration among advertisers when selecting which station to advertise and that they are happy with the services of the radio advertising. Likewise, the digital broadcasting revealed a moderate influence both on sales and on market shares. The absence of differences on the extent of advertising influence to sales and market shares, the extent of radio selection factors, and the extent of advertisers' satisfaction is also evident. Further, the findings revealed no significant difference between the advertising package and sales and between advertising package and market shares. The study's findings enable radio advertisers and radio stations to investigate novel programs and marketing strategies that will support business operations and boost profit margins year after year.

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INTRODUCTION

Currently, radio is still regarded as the most pervasive, persuasive, and credible medium for news in the nation. With over 25 million sets in the country, the National Telecommunications and Information Administration asserts that radio reaches 85 to 90% of the population. Radio households are estimated to number 10.2 million out of the 12 million total households in the country, compared to only 3.6 million households with a videocassette recorder and 8.52 million households with a television. In addition, estimates from the radio industry suggest that people listen to radio for two to three hours per day on average.

The economy, government, interest groups, and society as a whole are all parts of a larger environment that is influenced by a network of forces. This environment also includes advertisers, agencies, the media, and audiences. According to Arens (2015), the most basic feature of advertising is a means of communicating with customers about a product.

According to Kalotra (2013), the mass media are crucial in connecting people from all over the world. It has the ability to convey powerful, societally relevant messages to a large audience. Television and radio have had an impact on people's daily routines and content, as well as when they watch and listen to them. New media, which is altering audience participation habits, has challenged these distinctive characteristics of traditional media.

According to Hirsh (2013), radio broadcast has proven to be a long-lasting means for both large and small businesses to advertise their goods and services despite the proliferation of digital media. According to the Radio Advertising Bureau, industry revenue in the United States was approximately \$14.2 billion in 2012, up 1% from 2011. According to research, radio ads can influence a variety of station formats to reach targeted audiences, particularly during "drive time" and other times when listening to the radio is frequently a daily habit.

This may account for the fact that the majority of advertisements direct customers to retail stores where products can be purchased. As a result, retailers engage in extensive promotional activities, particularly through radio and other forms of media.

A study by Rajagopal (2010) revealed that a large number of people listen to radio while doing other things, which means that many of these people are also rural and urban dwellers. As a result, many products and services receive large-scale radio advertisements.

According to Awunyo-Vitor, D., et al. (2013)'s study, radio communication has evolved into a fertile ground for product and service advertising with the aim of increasing sales. Nevertheless, it is essential to keep in mind that sales are influenced by a variety of other factors in addition to advertising, such as the product's features, price, availability, and competitors' actions.

Clow et al. claim that (2008), radio's influence on advertising and listenership have never been disputed. For instance, in the United States, more than 235 million people listen to radio each week, with more than 92% of people over the age of 12 doing so. However, urban commuters have returned to radio listening as a source of mobile entrainment due to recent media preferences.

Backhaus (2019) says that audience members most value programming and activities that are based on listening to their needs and interests and are deeply rooted in the contextual environment of the community for community radio stations working within a development agenda. The broader repercussions of these findings shed light on how stations can plan events and programming to deeply connect with their audiences and establish themselves as a significant player in the local media landscape.

Yusuff (2009) emphasizes that radio advertising was used for the majority of short and informative advertisements for consumer goods in urban settings, appealing to consumers' psychological well-being and product efficacy. In a nutshell, radio's extensive reach to urban listener demographics makes it an ideal medium for fast-moving consumer goods marketing.

Alan May (2013) asserts that one reason radio is still relevant to advertisers is the actual ad format. Securing even 30 seconds of dedicated user attention, let alone 60 seconds, in a world where web page consumption can be as short as a few seconds, is a remarkable achievement. Most importantly, the format actively disseminates content to audiences, enabling a more complex sales message to be communicated. Humor, music, celebrity endorsements, offers, calls to action, web addresses, phone numbers, and, of course, those all-too-common lightning-fast disclosures are all ways to improve advertisements!

Currently, radio is still regarded as the most pervasive, persuasive, and credible medium and the primary news source in the nation. With over 25 million sets in the country, the National Telecommunications and Information Administration asserts that radio reaches 85 to 90% of the population. It stated that of the 12 million households that are estimated to exist all over the country, 10.2 million have radios, while only 3.6 million households have videocassette recorders and 8.52 million households have televisions.

The preceding environment presents a challenge for local radio platforms or stations that appear unprepared. As a result, the goal of this study was to figure out how ready digital broadcasting was and address issues that would lead to other studies that focus on customer satisfaction and relevant advertising influences and factors. In particular, it will investigate the impact of the current platform on sales, profit, and market share; Cost, rating, signal, and program content are all advertising factors taken into consideration; and the contentment of customers.

Research Problem

The goal of this study was to determine perceived influence of radio advertisement, selection factors, and client satisfaction of radio broadcasting.

The study specifically pursued the following objectives: How many years of radio advertising experience do radio advertisers have, what kind of business they work in, what kind of clients they serve, and what advertising packages they use? How does the radio advertisement appear to affect the revenue and market share of advertisers? What factors influence advertisers' radio station selection decisions? How pleased are radio advertisers to what extent? How much of an impact does digital broadcasting have on revenue and market share? When advertisers are grouped by profile, does the influence of radio advertising on their revenue differ significantly? When advertisers are grouped by profile, does the influence of radio advertising on advertisers' market share differ significantly? When advertisers are grouped according to the profile, is there a significant difference in the amount of factor selection consideration that advertisers give and the degree to which advertisers are satisfied?

Statement of Hypotheses

At the 0.05 level of significance, the following hypotheses were drawn in relation to the aforementioned issues: When advertisers are grouped according to the profile, there is no significant correlation between the perceived influence of radio advertising and their revenue. When advertisers are grouped by profile, there is no significant correlation between the perceived influence of radio advertising and advertisers' market share. When advertisers are grouped by profile, their factor selection considerations are not significantly different; Additionally, when advertisers are grouped according to the profile, there is no significant difference in the degree to which they are satisfied.

Methodology

Research Design

The study's objective was to determine the radio advertisement influence, radio-selection factors, and advertisers' satisfaction of radio broadcasting in Bacolod City. With reference to the nature of the study, the researchers considered the use of descriptive research design. Desk research was additionally used to establish the study's baseline and was gathered from the Internet, public libraries, journals, and compiled studies.

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework of the Study

Similarly, field research was also used primarily during the fieldwork of collecting data to the different radio advertisers. The researchers themselves conducted the fieldwork consisting of a survey and interviews of respondents-advertisers. In constructing the questionnaire or interview guide, the researchers used the questions raised in the statement of the problem as the guide.

Results and Discussion

Radio is an appealing publicizing mechanism because of reasons other than its conveyance of a homogenous crowd. With these, promoters partake in the specialization of radio since it gives them admittance to homogenous gatherings of audience members to whom items can be pitched. A crowd of people faithful to a particular configuration station is probably faithful to the individuals who publicize on it. With the multiplication of web and the virtual entertainment, radio broadcasts must be kept refreshed on the sort of promoters there getting to guarantee its business manageability. Table 1.0 beneath is the profile of the members of the review.

The table showed that 33.3 and 25.9 percent of the advertisers are from distribution and consumer goods and services business, respectively. In terms of organizational form, 96.3 percent are corporate where 59.3 percent are engaged in advertising from 1-7 years and 40.7 percent are from eight to 14 years. Eighty nine percent of the

advertisers are existing clients. As to advertising package, 51.9 percent of the advertisers preferred the regular program while 40.7 percent are for both regular and primetime programs.

Table 2.0 The Extent of Influence to Revenue.

Variable Groupings	Mean	Standard Deviation	Interpretation
<i>A. As a Whole</i>	3.59	.27331	High
<i>B. Nature of Business</i>			
Manufacturing	3.54	.59073	High
Service	3.60	.22361	High
Retailing	3.88	-	High
Distribution	3.46	.27951	High
Financial Services	3.56	.08839	High
Consumer Goods & Services	3.70	.12199	High
<i>C. Form of Organization</i>			
Partnership	2.87	-	Moderate
Corporation	3.61	.23899	High
<i>D. Length of Advertising Engagement</i>			
1-7 years	3.57	.26208	High
8 – 14 years	3.59	.30151	High
<i>E. Client Type</i>			
Repeat Client	3.57	.27653	High
New Client	3.75	-	High
<i>F. Advertising Package</i>			
Regular Program	3.54	.27486	High
Primetime Program	3.81	.08839	High
Both Regular & Primetime	3.59	.28554	High

Scale:5-Very High, 4-High, 3-Moderate, 2-Low, 1-Very Low

The graphed revealed that when participants were grouped as a whole resulted as high with a mean score of 3.59. Generally, this result suggests that almost all variables on the extent of influence of advertisement to revenue considered as high. Specifically, under the nature of business, manufacturing, service, retailing, distribution, financial, and consumer goods and services revealed to be all high. Consecutively, it received mean scores 3.54, 3.60, 3.88, 3.46, 3.56, and 3.70. As to form of ownership, partnership resulted as moderate with a mean score of 2.87. On the other hand, a corporation resulted as high with a mean score of 3.61. With mean scores of 3.57 and 3.59, respectively, bracketed groups consisting of participants who had engaged in advertising for between one and seven years and between eight and fourteen years were the most successful. With mean scores of 3.57 and 3.75 consecutively, advertisers' influence on sales was high according to client type—repeat customer or new client.

Last but not least, when advertisers were divided into subscription advertising packages, they received mean scores of 3.54 for the regular program, 3.81 for the primetime program, and 3.59 for advertisers who subscribed to both the regular and primetime programs. However, in general, all mean scores indicated a significant impact on advertisers' revenue from radio advertising. This indicates that despite respondents being divided into multiple categories, radio advertising still has a significant impact on advertisers' revenue.

Ayimey, Vitor, and Gadawusun (2013) conducted the research titled "Does Radio Advertising Influence the Sale of Herbal Products in Ghana?" According to the findings of the "Evidence from Ho Municipality," 80 percent of advertisers believe that advertising makes a product popular, and 20 percent believe that advertising aids in product sales, the findings somewhat suggest that radio advertisements influence sales. It would appear from these perceptions that advertising has a significant impact on sales.

Radio has come a long way since its first widespread crackling across the airwaves 100 years ago. Today, radio is a powerful tool for brands and businesses to connect with customers and entertain listeners around the world. In point of fact, a study conducted by Nielsen Catalina Solutions (NCS) demonstrated that investing in radio is prudent. It discovered a direct correlation between sales at physical stores and radio advertising. Researchers found

that listeners received an average sales return of \$6 for every dollar spent on advertisements 28 days after hearing them in this first major study on radio effectiveness. The study found that advertisers received an average return of \$6 for every \$1 spent, but that returns varied significantly across categories. Notably, the two retailers generated more than 10 and 23 times the high end return, whereas a soft drink brand and breakfast bar generated less than two times the low end return, despite providing positive returns on all investments.

Table 3 Extent of Advertisement Influence to Market Share

Variable Groupings	Mean	Standard Deviation	Interpretation
<i>A. As a Whole</i>	3.34	.32074	Moderate
<i>B. Nature of Business</i>			
Manufacturing	2.87	.54486	Moderate
Service	3.35	.24044	Moderate
Retailing	3.62	-	High
Distribution	3.31	.29389	Moderate
Financial Services	3.44	.08839	High
Consumer Goods & Services	3.52	.16815	High
<i>C. Form of Organization</i>			
Partnership	3.38	-	Moderate
Corporation	3.34	.32703	Moderate
<i>D. Length of Advertising Engagement</i>			
1-7 years	3.35	.27846	Moderate
8 – 14 years	3.33	.38840	Moderate
<i>E. Client Type</i>			
Repeat Client	3.33	.32199	Moderate
New Client	3.63	-	High
<i>F. Advertising Package</i>			
Regular Program	3.32	.26726	Moderate
Primetime Program	3.44	.26517	High
Both Regular & Primetime	3.35	.40627	Moderate

Scale:5-Very High, 4-High, 3-Moderate, 2-Low, 1-Very Low

The next goal of this research was to determine how much advertising influences market shares. According to Table 3, the average score for the impact of advertising on market shares was moderate (3.34). Manufacturing businesses received a mean score of 2.87, followed by services businesses with a 3.35 and distribution businesses with a 3.31. These average results are considered to be of moderate extent. The retailing, financial, and consumer goods and services sectors, on the other hand, produced mean scores of 3.62, 3.44, and 3.52, respectively, all of which were interpreted as high extent. Both partnerships and corporations, which have the same organizational forms, received mean scores of 3.38 and 3.34, respectively, which are considered to be of a moderate extent. similarly strong a bearing on market shares.

The findings from the study "Does Radio Advertising Influence Sale of Herbal Products in Ghana? According to a 2013 study titled "Evidence from Ho Municipality," which was conducted by Edward Kwame Ayimey, Dadson Awunyo-Vitor, and John Korbla Gadawusu, radio is the best medium for marketing herbal products because it can reach a large number of people who belong to a company's target market in urban, semi-urban, and rural areas. The study shows that radio advertisements for herbal products affect the kinds of products purchased because they offer crucial information that influences purchasing choices.

An international study titled Role of Radio Advertisements as Behavioral Driver among Urban Consumers found a dyadic relationship between the volume of purchases and store preference based on the consumer experience and strength of radio advertisement influence. During the study, it was found that radio listeners (urban commuters) were drawn to the advertisements that were more entertaining while still getting the point across. They frequently looked forward to these commercials, not just for the entertainment but also to carefully analyze the message and weigh the pros and cons. Because it can reach a wide range of targeted listener demographics in urban environments, radio is the perfect medium for marketing fast-moving consumer goods.

Radio commercials that are anchored by new methods have become effective tools for public hearing and cross-cultural communication (O'Donnell, 2009). Radio is now acknowledged as the most pervasive, convincing, and reliable medium for news. With more than 25 million sets nationwide, it reaches 85% to 90% of the population (Ramon R. Tuazo, 2015). Thus, this study demonstrates that radio advertising boosts the market shares of all companies that use it.

Table 4.0 Extent of Radio Selection Factors

Variable Groupings	Ads Cost	Radio Ratings	Signal	Program Content	Digital Radio
<i>A. As a Whole</i>	4.41	4.19	3.78	3.67	3.44
<i>B. Nature of Business</i>					
Manufacturing	4.33	4.33	3.33	3.00	3.33
Service	4.60	4.40	4.20	4.60	4.20
Retailing	4.00	4.00	3.00	3.00	3.00
Distribution	4.33	4.00	3.78	3.56	3.67
Financial Services	4.00	4.00	3.00	3.00	3.00
Consumer Goods & Services	4.57	4.71	4.00	3.71	2.86
<i>C. Form of Organization</i>					
Partnership	5.00	5.00	5.00	5.00	5.00
Corporation	4.38	4.15	3.73	3.62	3.38
<i>D. Length of Advertising Engagement</i>					
1 – 7 years	4.44	4.25	3.88	3.75	3.50
8 – 14 years	4.36	4.09	3.64	3.55	3.36
<i>E. Client Type</i>					
Repeat Client	4.38	4.15	3.73	3.62	3.46
New Client	5.00	5.00	5.00	5.00	5.00
<i>F. Advertising Package</i>					
Regular Program	4.36	4.07	3.86	3.86	3.79
Primetime Program	5.00	5.00	4.50	4.50	3.00
Both Regular & Primetime	4.36	4.18	3.55	3.27	3.09

Scale: 5-Very High, 4-High, 3-Moderate, 2-Low, 1-Very Low

Finding out the extent of radio selection factors among advertisers was the fourth investigational goal. When radio selection factors are taken together, the cost of advertising yielded the highest mean score of 4.41. With mean scores of 4.19, 3.78, 3.67, and 3.44, respectively, radio ratings, signal strength, program content, and the availability of digital radio technology come next. Table 4 specifically demonstrates that manufacturing (4.33), service (4.60), distribution (4.33), and consumer goods and services (4.57) all showed very high extents of radio selection factors in relation to the cost of advertisement. The average scores for retail and financial services were both 4.00, which is considered to be of high extent. Both partnerships and corporations are acceptable forms of organization.

With mean scores of 4.44 and 4.36, respectively, the bracketed groups 1 to 7 years and 8 to 14 years also exhibit a very high extent in cost as a radio selection factor when it comes to variable, length of advertising engagement. Repeat customers and new customers produced mean scores of 4.38 and 5.00 under the category of client types, both of which are considered to be very high. While on all ad packages, regular programming aired at 4.36, primetime programming aired at 5.00, and regular and primetime advertisers aired at 4.36, revealing a very high extent. The regular program started at 4.36, the primetime program started at 5.00, and both regular advertisers and primetime advertisers started at 4.36 on all advertising packages. Businesses in the service (4.40) and consumer goods and services (4.71) categories said that radio rating was a big factor in their decision-making. The remainder were only displayed to a significant degree. The corporation produced a very high percentage, while the partnership produced a very high percentage (5.00). The most typical lengths of advertising engagement were eight to fourteen years (4.09) and one to seven years (4.25). Radio ratings for new clients were very high (5.00), while ratings for returning clients were also very high (3.73). Regular advertisers (4.07) and both regular and primetime advertisers (4.18) had high extents while included in the advertising package, with the exception of primetime advertisers (5.00), which had a very high extent.

Under the nature of business, services (4.20), distribution (3.78), and consumer goods and services (4.00) scored highly in terms of signal, while the rest had moderate scores. In terms of business structure, corporations (3.73)

and partnerships (5.00) both performed well. Both 1 to 7 years (3.88) and 8 to 14 years (3.64) had the highest levels of engagement with advertisements. Regarding client type, the proportion of new clients (5.00) was extremely high, whereas the proportion of repeat clients (3.62) was also high. When classified as radio signal dimensions, advertisers had similar mean interpretations as they did under the radio rating dimension. The radio signal was selected to a very high extent by the primetime program advertisers (4.5). Regular programming scored a 3.86, and both regular and primetime advertisers scored a 3.55.

When choosing a radio, the extent to which the business was service-based was very high, with a mean program content score of 4.60. Retailing (3.00) and financial services (3.00) came in at a moderate level, with distribution business (3.56) and consumer goods and services (3.71) coming in at a high level. Grouped according to ownership structure, corporations (3.62) and partnerships (5.00) both had high extent. Both 1 to 7 years (3.75) and 8 to 14 years (3.55) of advertisement engagement on bracketed groups produced high extents. Regarding client type, the extent to which repeat clients (3.62) and new client advertisers (5.00) used program content as a deciding factor in their advertising decisions, respectively, was very high. Primetime advertisers had a very high impact on program content (4.5), compared to regular advertisers (3.86), primetime advertisers (3.27), and both regular and primetime advertisers (3.86).

The service business (4.20) and distribution (3.67) resulted to a high extent when the nature of business variables led to the availability of digital broadcasting services in the selection factor. However, moderate extents were reported in manufacturing (3.33), retailing (3.00), financial services (2.86), and consumer goods and services (2.86). When treated as a partnership (5.00) and a corporation (3.38), respectively, the former produced a very high extent while the latter produced a moderate extent. When the advertisers calculated the length of service, the bracketed groups 1 to 7 years (3.50) and 8 to 14 years (3.36), respectively, calculated high and moderate results. When advertisers were evaluated based on the type of client, new clients (5.00) showed up to a very high extent, while repeat clients (3.46) showed up to a high extent. Regular advertisers performed well (3.79), but primetime and dual advertisers (3.00) performed only moderately when they were combined into advertising packages. As stated by Turow J. (2010), Radio is a desirable advertising medium for reasons other than its ability to deliver a homogeneous audience, according to Introduction to Mass Media Communication: Media Literacy and Culture (2010). Radio advertisements can be updated, changed, and tailored to different times of the day because they are inexpensive to produce. Those who advertise on a station with a particular format are likely to have a loyal audience. Radio is the friend of the listener; it goes places with them and speaks directly to them.

Table 5.0 Extent of Radio Advertisers’ Satisfaction

Variable Groupings	Mean	Standard Deviation	Interpretation
<i>A. As a Whole</i>	3.70	.52164	High
<i>B. Nature of Business</i>			
Manufacturing	3.38	1.48690	Moderate
Service	3.91	.31298	High
Retailing	3.43	-	High
Distribution	3.81	.34256	High
Financial Services	3.43	.20203	High
Consumer Goods & Services	3.65	.25895	High
<i>C. Form of Organization</i>			
Partnership	4.57	-	Very High
Corporation	3.66	.50133	High
<i>D. Length of Advertising Engagement</i>			
1-7 years	3.69	.30957	High
8 – 14 years	3.71	.75051	High
<i>E. Client Type</i>			
Repeat Client	3.69	.52841	High
New Client	4.00	-	High
<i>F. Advertising Package</i>			
Regular Program	3.73	.37108	High
Primetime Program	4.00	-	High
Both Regular & Primetime	3.60	.70514	High

Scale: 5-Very High, 4-High, 3-Moderate, 2-Low, 1-Very Low

The fifth objective of this study was to examine the extent of the advertisers' satisfaction as a whole and according to present variables. The investigation revealed that generally the advertisers, collecting a mean score of 3.70, expressed high extent of satisfaction. When they treated as to nature of business, all business types resulted as high extent of satisfaction, except for manufacturing business which collected a mean score of 3.38, interpreted as moderate. Specifically, service business garnered a mean score of 3.91; retailing, 3.43; distribution, 3.81; financial services, 3.43; and consumer goods and services, 3.65. The advertisers under the partnership form of business resulted as very high satisfaction with a mean score of 4.67 while advertisers under the corporation resulted as high satisfaction with a mean score of 3.66. Inspection of the results when advertisers were categorized according to length of advertising engagement revealed that advertisers both belonging to 1-to-7-year brackets and 8-to-14-year brackets showed as high satisfaction with mean scores 3.69 and 4.00 respectively. As to client type, whether new or repeat clients also showed as high satisfaction with mean scores of 3.69 and 4.00 respectively. When advertisers were grouped into advertising packages, all of the groupings, regular program advertisers (3.73), primetime program advertisers (4.00), and dual program advertisers (3.60) resulted as high satisfaction.

Table 6.0 Extent of Influence of Digital Broadcasting to Revenue

Variable Groupings	Mean	Standard Deviation	Interpretation
<i>A. As a Whole</i>	3.33	.38844	Moderate
<i>B. Nature of Business</i>			
Manufacturing	2.96	.93819	Moderate
Service	3.50	.25000	High
Retailing	3.00	-	Moderate
Distribution	3.54	.21304	High
Financial Services	3.19	.26517	Moderate
Consumer Goods & Services	3.25	.19094	Moderate
<i>C. Form of Organization</i>			
Partnership	3.75	-	High
Corporation	3.31	.38660	Moderate
<i>D. Length of Advertising Engagement</i>			
1-7 years	3.40	.29080	Moderate
8 – 14 years	3.24	.48559	Moderate
<i>E. Client Type</i>			
Repeat Client	3.33	.39668	Moderate
New Client	3.78	-	High
<i>F. Advertising Package</i>			
Regular Program	3.19	.26517	Moderate
Primetime Program	4.00	.00000	High
Both Regular & Primetime	3.60	.70514	High

Scale:5-Very High, 4-High, 3-Moderate, 2-Low, 1-Very Low

The investigation's sixth objective was to ascertain the extent to which digital broadcasting affects revenue. With a mean score of 3.33, digital broadcasting has a moderate impact, as shown in Table 6. Analyzing the data revealed that digital broadcasting has a significant impact on distribution and service-based businesses, with mean scores of 3.50 and 3.54, respectively. Manufacturing came in at 2.96, retailing came in at 3.00, financial services came in at 3.19, and consumer goods and services came in at 3.25. With a mean score of 3.75, digital broadcasting had a significant impact on sales for partnership-based businesses. With a mean score of 3.31, the business of the corporation was established to a moderate extent.

Additionally, both bracketed groups were moderately exposed in terms of the length of advertising engagement, with mean scores of 3.40 and 3.24 respectively. According to client classification, the average scores were high for new clients (3.78) and moderate for repeat clients (3.33). Additionally, the levels of influence of digital broadcasting sales were high for advertisers who ran ads during primetime programs (4.00) and for dual programs (3.60), but only to a moderate extent for advertisers of regular programs.

Table 7.0 Extent of Influence of Digital Broadcasting to Market Shares

Variable Groupings	Mean	Standard Deviation	Interpretation
<i>A. As a Whole</i>	3.23	.47418	Moderate
<i>B. Nature of Business</i>			
Manufacturing	2.75	1.11102	Moderate
Service	3.45	.40117	High
Retailing	3.00	-	Moderate
Distribution	3.38	.27951	Moderate
Financial Services	3.19	.26517	Moderate
Consumer Goods & Services	3.18	.31339	Moderate
<i>C. Form of Organization</i>			
Partnership	3.75	-	High
Corporation	3.21	.47156	Moderate
<i>D. Length of Advertising Engagement</i>			
1-7 years	3.34	.36830	Moderate
8 - 14 years	3.09	.57034	Moderate
<i>E. Client Type</i>			
Repeat Client	3.24	.48190	Moderate
New Client	3.00	-	Moderate
<i>F. Advertising Package</i>			
Regular Program	3.42	.30847	High
Primetime Program	3.00	.00000	Moderate
Both Regular & Primetime	3.02	.60035	Moderate

Scale: 5-Very High, 4-High, 3-Moderate, 2-Low, 1-Very Low

Another objective of this study was to determine the extent of influence of digital broadcasting to market shares. With a mean score of 3.23, Table 7 illustrates the extent of digital broadcasting's influence on market shares, which is interpreted as moderate. With the exception of service-based businesses, which came out as high extent with a mean score of 3.45, the mean scores when advertisers were grouped according to their nature of business were revealed as moderate. Given that advertisers were divided into partnership and corporation types of businesses, the former had a mean score of 3.75, while the latter had a mean score of 3.21, which were interpreted as having high and moderate levels of influence, respectively, on their market shares, from the perspective of digital broadcasting. Looking at the same table, advertisers in the age brackets of 1 to 7 and 8 to 14 years all revealed a moderate extent of perceived influence on the market shares of digital broadcasting.

Regarding the client type variables, it appears that both advertisers obtained mean scores of 3.24 and 3.00, which are interpreted as moderately influencing the market share for digital broadcasting when grouped as repeat and new clients. While primetime program advertisers with a mean score of 3.00 and dual program advertisers with a mean score of 3.02 revealed as moderate on the influence of digital broadcasting as to its market share when they were categorized to the advertising package they secure. The average score for the regular program advertisers was 3.42, which was considered to be of a high extent.

Table 8.0 Difference in the Extent of Advertising Influence to Revenue

Variable Groupings	p-value	Interpretation
<i>A. Nature of Business</i>	.318	Not Significant
<i>B. Form of Organization</i>	.103	Not Significant
<i>C. Length of Advertising Engagement</i>	.074	Not Significant
<i>D. Client Type</i>	.593	Not Significant
<i>E. Advertising Package</i>	.240	Not Significant

The eighth goal of this research was to identify any notable variations in the strength of advertising's impact on sales when advertisers were grouped according to particular criteria. The p-values for the business type, organizational structure, duration of the advertising contract, client type, and advertising package are displayed in Table 10 at .318, .103, .074, .593, and .240. No real differences were found for any of the mentioned variables. Accepted

is the hypothesis that, when all the preselected variables are taken into account, there is no appreciable difference in the degree of advertising influence on sales.

Table 9.0 Difference in the Extent of Advertising Influence to Market Shares

Variable Groupings	p-value	Interpretation
<i>A. Nature of Business</i>	.235	Not Significant
<i>B. Form of Organization</i>	.815	Not Significant
<i>C. Length of Advertising Engagement</i>	.680	Not Significant
<i>D. Client Type</i>	.296	Not Significant
<i>E. Advertising Package</i>	.596	Not Significant

The extent of advertising's impact on market shares when advertisers were grouped according to predetermined variables was another focus of the investigation. P-values are displayed for each grouping of variables in Table 10. The p-values for the business type, organizational structure, duration of the advertisement engagement, client type, and advertising package were .235, .815, .680, .296 and .596. When the recorded p-values are grouped in accordance with the identified variables, there are no discernible differences in the magnitude of influence on market shares. In other words, the idea that there is no appreciable variation in the amount of advertising influence on market shares is accepted.

Table 10.0 Differences in the Extent of Radio Selection Factors

Variable Groupings	p-value	Interpretation
<i>A. Nature of Business</i>	.212	Not Significant
<i>B. Form of Organization</i>	.105	Not Significant
<i>C. Length of Advertising Engagement</i>	.074	Not Significant
<i>D. Client Type</i>	.296	Not Significant
<i>E. Advertising Package</i>	.295	Not Significant

Finding the significant difference in the scope of radio selection factors was the study's tenth goal. With mean scores of .212, .105, .074, .296, and .295, Table 10 shows the results of the differences in the extent of radio selection factors when grouped by the advertisers' nature of business, form of organization, length of advertising engagement, client type, and advertising package. The extent of radio selection factors is not significantly differentiable by the obtained values. As a result, it is accepted that there are no appreciable differences in the extent of radio selection factors.

Table 11.0 Differences in the Extent of Advertiser's Satisfaction

Variable Groupings	Mean	Standard Deviation	Interpretation
<i>A. As a Whole</i>	3.59	.27331	High
<i>B. Nature of Business</i>			
Manufacturing	3.54	.59073	High
Service	3.60	.22361	High
Retailing	3.88	-	High
Distribution	3.46	.27951	High
Financial Services	3.56	.08839	High
Consumer Goods & Services	3.70	.12199	High
<i>C. Form of Organization</i>			
Partnership	2.87	-	Moderate
Corporation	3.61	.23899	High
<i>D. Length of Advertising Engagement</i>			
1-7 years	3.57	.26208	High
8-14 years	3.59	.30151	High
<i>E. Client Type</i>			
Repeat Client	3.57	.27653	High
New Client	3.75	-	High
<i>F. Advertising Package</i>			
Regular Program	3.54	.27486	High
Primetime Program	3.81	.08839	High
Both Regular & Primetime	3.59	.28554	High

The investigation's final goal was to find out how satisfied the advertisers were with the service that the radio station was offering on various fronts. Detailing the level of the advertisers' satisfaction is shown in Table 11. The obtained p-values for the following variables on this table were interpreted as not significant: .269 for the nature of the advertisers' business; .100 for the form of organization; .160 for the length of the advertising engagement; .444 for the client type; and .312 for the advertising package. Accepted is the hypothesis that there are no appreciable variations in the level of advertiser satisfaction.

Conclusions

The following conclusions are drawn in light of the investigation's findings. Radio advertising has a favorable impact on sales and a moderate impact on market shares. When choosing the station to advertise on, advertisers give the most weight to the cost of the advertisements. Advertisers are pleased with the station's current offerings. Digital broadcasting has a minor impact on market shares and sales. Sales and market shares are unrelated to the advertising package. Not every variable affects sales and market shares. Not all variables play a role in radio station selection. Not every variable affects how satisfied advertisers are.

Implications

Based on the investigation's findings and recommendations, the following implications are drawn. In general, radio advertisements have a significant impact. In particular, radio advertising has a strong impact on sales but a limited impact on market shares. Increases in the number and volume of transactions make it simple to account for and observe changes in sales, but it is more difficult and time-consuming to measure market shares. In order to increase sales and market shares, this suggests to advertisers that they still should have spent more on advertising. This indicates to radio stations that radio is still a powerful tool for persuading consumers to purchase goods. In general, radio selection factors are regarded as important, with the cost of advertising receiving special attention. This suggests that the radio station must rationalize its cost structure in order to attract more advertisers. The satisfaction of advertisers is generally high. According to this viewpoint, it follows that the station must continue to fulfill customer needs or go above and beyond to do so in order to keep and earn their loyalty. Digital broadcasting has a moderate impact on sales and market sales. The potential of the technology is still untapped. The advertisers must be told with emphasis on its capabilities and marketing potential. Sales and market shares are unrelated to advertising packages. This could indicate that there are irregularities in the programs' content, the timing of their advertisements, and the volume of listeners. According to advertisers, there is little difference between how much advertising influences sales and markets. This suggests that more needs to be done so that advertisers can distinguish in a concrete way how radio advertisements affect their sales and market shares. The degree of radio selection factors is not significantly different from one another. This finding suggests that when choosing a radio station, the selection factors are equally significant. In terms of how satisfied advertisers are, there is no discernible difference. This suggests that their level of satisfaction is the same regardless of how they are classified.

Recommendations

Regarding the investigation's findings, conclusions, and implications, the following suggestions are made. To fully maximize the impact and influence of radio advertising on increasing sales and market shares of their products, advertisers should package considerations like appropriate program content, advertisement placement or timing, and listener traffic. To determine which of the station's programs are being listened to by listeners, ongoing research or surveys can be conducted there. By doing this, advertisers could receive recommendations on tactics. Advertisers may be given incentives or a rationalized, graduated pricing structure. The gradual implementation of improvements in areas like signal, program content, radio ratings, and technological upgrade is possible. Prioritizing appropriate budget allocation in order to accomplish this goal is also necessary.

In order to keep a customer or develop a loyal following, they must be satisfied. Customer satisfaction results in recommendations, positive word-of-mouth, and unpaid promotion of the radio station. To increase the satisfaction of advertisers, it is possible to study and afford incentives, special or exciting packages, and programs that depend on the advertisers' loyalty or length of engagement with the station, packages used, client type, type of account, number or volume of advertisements, and many others. Utilizing information drive, it is important to highlight how digital broadcasting technology can increase sales and market share in station-sponsored advertisements. Free trials of digital services can help them understand and gauge how they will affect their sales and market shares.

The goal of highly-priced advertising packages is to maximize the reach of a company's or product's advertisement in relation to listener traffic and program content. Customers, and especially premium program advertisers, anticipate that the majority of the money spent on advertising will result in higher sales or a larger share of the market. The system may have flaws that can be discovered through reevaluation or monitoring of this aspect. Once more, it's critical that advertisers understand the distinction between, say, subscribing to the length of an advertisement or selecting a spot, or else all advertisers would choose standard offerings. This entails a decrease in the station's integrity, a clientele loss, and perhaps a decrease in revenue. The management of the radio station should analyze the situation and create fresh plans that could actually make a difference. When the determining factors for radio station selection are identical, it is necessary to capitalize on something distinctive that advertisers or clients seek in a station's advertising. It is important to develop a brand appropriately so that it sticks in the minds of customers. Customers, both old and new, are pleased with the success of the company. However, premium inducements are crucial. Economic theory states that "people respond to incentives." Based on this premise, suitable incentives for each client's situation should be researched and developed to produce satisfied customers.

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